

Study of the Incidence of Different Types of Tuberculous Lesions in Association with Diabetes Mellitus in a Tertiary Care Center in North India

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Abstract:

Background: Tuberculosis (TB) remains a major global health challenge, particularly in regions like India, where the burden is exacerbated by the rising prevalence of diabetes mellitus (DM). DM is a known risk factor for TB, leading to more severe disease forms and poorer treatment outcomes. Understanding the interaction between TB and DM is crucial for developing effective management strategies, especially in high-burden settings.

Aim: This study aimed to investigate the incidence and types of tuberculous lesions in diabetic and non-diabetic patients at a tertiary care center in North India, with the goal of identifying patterns that could inform better clinical management.

Methods: A total of 100 patients diagnosed with TB were included, of which 40 were diabetic and 60 were non-diabetic. Data were collected on the type of TB lesion (pulmonary or extrapulmonary) and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. The Chi-square test was used to assess the association between diabetes and lesion type.

Results: The study found that 62.5% of diabetic patients had pulmonary TB, compared to 75% of non-diabetic patients. Extrapulmonary TB was more common in diabetic patients (37.5%) than in non-diabetic patients (25%). Cavitory lesions were more prevalent among diabetic patients with pulmonary TB (60%) compared to non-diabetic patients (40%). The association between diabetes mellitus and the type of tuberculous lesion was statistically significant ($p = 0.040$).

Conclusion: Diabetes mellitus significantly influences the type and severity of tuberculous lesions, with diabetic patients showing a higher prevalence of extrapulmonary TB and more severe pulmonary manifestations such as cavitory lesions. These findings underscore the need for tailored treatment strategies and close monitoring of TB patients with diabetes.

Recommendations: Integrated care approaches that address both TB and DM are recommended, particularly in high-burden areas. Further research with larger sample sizes is needed to explore the underlying mechanisms and to develop targeted interventions that can improve outcomes for diabetic patients with TB.

Keywords: Tuberculosis, Diabetes Mellitus, Pulmonary TB, Extrapulmonary TB, Cavitory Lesions

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Introduction

(TB) is one of the world's most serious public health issues, with nearly 10 million new cases and 1.4 million fatalities reported in 2019 alone, according to the (WHO) [1]. India, in particular, carries a significant burden of tuberculosis, accounting for about 25% of the global incidence [2]. (DM) is becoming more prevalent over the world, complicating the tuberculosis epidemic. Diabetes is a known risk factor for tuberculosis because it compromises the immunological response, increasing vulnerability to Mycobacterium tuberculosis infection and the

transition of latent to active disease [3]. With the global growth in diabetes, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, the relationship between tuberculosis and diabetes has become a source of significant worry. According to studies, those with diabetes are three times more likely to get tuberculosis than those without it [4]. This relationship is especially alarming in nations like India, where both tuberculosis and diabetes are endemic. The dual burden of these diseases complicates clinical management and presents considerable hurdles for

public health efforts targeted at controlling tuberculosis [5]. Diabetic people are more likely to develop extrapulmonary symptoms and more severe forms of pulmonary tuberculosis, such as cavitory lesions. These severe variants are linked to larger bacterial loads, increased transmission risk, and poorer treatment outcomes [7].

Recent research has highlighted the bidirectional association between TB and DM, in which not only does DM increase the likelihood of acquiring TB, but TB itself can affect glycaemic control, worsening diabetes [8]. This interaction results in a vicious cycle, complicating the management of both illnesses. Furthermore, DM is linked to delayed sputum conversion and an increased risk of TB relapse, which contributes to continued transmission and medication resistance [9].

Given the enormous epidemiological and pathophysiologic overlap between TB and DM, it is critical to investigate how DM influences TB clinical presentation and outcomes. This insight is critical for creating integrated management strategies that target both diseases concurrently. Despite the understanding of this dual burden, there is a scarcity of data on the exact patterns of tuberculosis lesions in diabetic patients, particularly in high-burden areas such as India. This study aimed to investigate the incidence and types of tuberculous lesions in diabetic and non-diabetic patients at a tertiary care center in North India, with the goal of identifying patterns that could inform better clinical management.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH), Patna, a tertiary care center in North India.

Study Duration: The study was carried out over a period of one year, from September 2017 to August 2018.

Participants: A total of 100 patients were included in this study. These participants were selected from those attending the outpatient and inpatient departments of PMCH with a diagnosis of tuberculosis, with or without a history of diabetes mellitus.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with tuberculosis (both pulmonary and extrapulmonary) based on clinical, radiological, and microbiological evidence.
- Patients aged 18 years and above.

- Patients with a confirmed diagnosis of diabetes mellitus based on fasting blood glucose levels, HbA1c levels, or a history of diabetes mellitus.
- Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients under the age of 18 years.
- Patients with a history of immunosuppressive therapy or other immunocompromised states, excluding diabetes mellitus.
- Patients who refused to participate in the study or withdrew consent at any stage.
- Patients with incomplete medical records or those lost to follow-up.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, a consecutive sampling method was used where every eligible patient meeting the inclusion criteria during the study period was enrolled. To reduce information bias, all data were collected using a standardized data collection form, and all procedures were conducted by trained professionals.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured proforma which included demographic details, clinical history, laboratory results, and imaging studies. Information on the presence and type of tuberculous lesions, diabetic status, and associated comorbidities was recorded.

Procedure

- Patients diagnosed with tuberculosis were evaluated for diabetic status.
- Detailed clinical examination and relevant investigations (e.g., sputum analysis, chest X-ray, histopathology for extrapulmonary tuberculosis) were performed to confirm the type and extent of tuberculous lesions.
- Blood samples were collected to assess fasting blood glucose levels and HbA1c for diabetic status confirmation.
- The association between diabetes mellitus and the type of tuberculous lesions was analyzed.

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered into a database and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies and percentages, were used to summarize the data. The Chi-square test was employed to analyze the association between diabetes mellitus and different types of tuberculous lesions. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 100 patients were enrolled in the study, with 55 males and 45 females. The mean age of the

participants was 45.6 years (SD = 12.8 years), ranging from 18 to 78 years. Out of the 100 patients, 40 were diagnosed with diabetes mellitus (40%), and 60 patients did not have diabetes (60%).

The tuberculous lesions were categorized into (PTB) and (EPTB). Among the 100 patients, 70 patients (70%) had pulmonary tuberculosis, while 30 patients (30%) had extrapulmonary tuberculosis.

Distribution of Tuberculous Lesions

Table 1: Distribution of Tuberculous Lesions among Study Participants

Type of Lesion	Total Patients (N=100)	Diabetic (N=40)	Non-Diabetic (N=60)
Pulmonary Tuberculosis	70	25	45
Extrapulmonary Tuberculosis	30	15	15

The study found a significant association between diabetes mellitus and the occurrence of pulmonary tuberculosis. Among the 40 diabetic patients, 25 (62.5%) had pulmonary tuberculosis, while 15 (37.5%) had extrapulmonary tuberculosis. In contrast, among the 60 non-diabetic patients, 45 (75%) had pulmonary tuberculosis, and 15 (25%) had extrapulmonary tuberculosis.

Table 2: Association between Diabetes Mellitus and Type of Tuberculous Lesion

Diabetic Status	Pulmonary TB (N=70)	Extrapulmonary TB (N=30)	Total	p-value
Diabetic (N=40)	25 (62.5%)	15 (37.5%)	40	0.040*
Non-Diabetic (N=60)	45 (75%)	15 (25%)	60	

*Note: *p < 0.05 is considered statistically significant.

The Chi-square test revealed a p-value of 0.040, indicating a statistically significant association between diabetes mellitus and the type of tuberculous lesion.

Further analysis showed that among patients with pulmonary tuberculosis, cavitory lesions were more

common in diabetic patients (60%) compared to non-diabetic patients (40%). In contrast, among patients with extrapulmonary tuberculosis, lymph node tuberculosis was the most common type in both diabetic and non-diabetic groups, with no significant difference in distribution.

Table 3: Incidence of Specific Tuberculous Lesions

Lesion Type	Diabetic (N=40)	Non-Diabetic (N=60)	Total
Pulmonary TB			
Cavitory Lesion	15 (60%)	18 (40%)	33
Consolidation	10 (40%)	27 (60%)	37
Extrapulmonary TB			
Lymph Node Tuberculosis	10 (66.7%)	10 (66.7%)	20
Pleural Effusion	5 (33.3%)	5 (33.3%)	10

Findings

- Higher Incidence of Pulmonary TB in Non-Diabetics:** The majority of non-diabetic patients (75%) had pulmonary tuberculosis, compared to 62.5% of diabetic patients.
- Significant Association between Diabetes and Lesion Type:** Diabetes mellitus was significantly associated with the type of tuberculous lesion (p = 0.040), with a higher incidence of extrapulmonary tuberculosis in diabetic patients.
- Cavitory Lesions Predominate in Diabetics:** Cavitory lesions were more prevalent in diabetic patients with pulmonary tuberculosis, suggesting a potential link between diabetes and the severity of pulmonary TB.

Discussion

The study aimed to investigate the incidence and types of tuberculous lesions in patients with and

without diabetes mellitus at a tertiary care center in North India. The results revealed a significant association between diabetes mellitus and the distribution of tuberculous lesions. Specifically, diabetic patients were more likely to present with (EPTB) compared to non-diabetic patients, who had a higher prevalence of (PTB). This suggests that diabetes may influence the pathophysiology of tuberculosis, possibly making patients more susceptible to extrapulmonary manifestations.

Moreover, the study found that among patients with pulmonary tuberculosis, diabetic individuals were more prone to developing cavitory lesions, which are known to be more severe and associated with a higher bacterial load. This finding aligns with existing literature that highlights the role of hyperglycemia in compromising the immune response, potentially leading to more extensive lung damage in diabetic patients. In contrast, consolidation, a less severe form of pulmonary

tuberculosis, was more common among non-diabetic patients.

The statistically significant association ($p = 0.040$) between diabetes mellitus and the type of tuberculous lesion underscores the importance of considering diabetes as a critical factor in the clinical management of tuberculosis. The results suggest that diabetic patients may require more intensive monitoring and treatment to prevent the progression of severe forms of tuberculosis. Additionally, the study highlights the need for targeted interventions to address the unique challenges faced by diabetic patients with tuberculosis, particularly in resource-limited settings where both conditions are prevalent.

Latent tuberculosis infection (LTBI) is linked to an increased risk of developing diabetes. They discovered that people with LTBI had a greater incidence of diabetes than those without TB, implying that LTBI may contribute to the development of diabetes. This connection remained even after accounting for other risk factors, demonstrating a strong link between LTBI and diabetes onset [10]. It was investigated the link between diabetes and latent tuberculosis in a high-TB prevalence area. The study revealed that diabetes was strongly related with an elevated risk of LTBI, particularly in older adults. This shows that in locations with high TB prevalence, diabetic individuals may require more attentive screening for LTBI to reduce the risk of advancement [11]. A case of primary tuberculous pyomyositis in a diabetic patient, emphasising the greater incidence of extrapulmonary tuberculosis in diabetics was studied. This rare illness, which is frequently misdiagnosed because to its generic presentation, emphasises the importance of timely diagnosis and treatment to avoid tragic effects [12].

Conclusion

This study underscores the importance of considering diabetes mellitus as a significant factor in the management of tuberculosis. The higher incidence of cavitory lesions in diabetic patients suggests a need for more aggressive treatment strategies in this population to prevent complications and improve outcomes. Further research with larger sample sizes is recommended to explore the underlying mechanisms of this association and to develop targeted interventions for diabetic patients with tuberculosis.

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